

POPULATION GROWTH, LAND USE PATTERN AND CHANGING OCCUPATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS IN SANGANER TEHSIL OF JAIPUR DISTRICT, RAJASTHAN

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ABSTRACT

Study of population is a very important aspect for geographers and regional planners. Population growth is an index of economic development. It is fundamental for understanding the correlation between the various demographic phenomena and the physio-cultural Environment. The detail of population of Sanganer tehsil shows that there is increased of 22 percent population in over the years. Watika, Muhana, Dahmi Kalan, Goner and Jaisinghpura are densely populated towns of the study area. Land use pattern is an outcome of natural and socio-economic factors and the analysis of these changes has become an important component in current strategies. Net sown area, Fallow land and Culturable waste land has subsequently declined while land put to non agricultural uses and built up areas increased during the span of four decades.

Occupational structure is a index of workers who are engaged in different activities. It is found that the amount of Fluoride has increased in water resources due to Textile Industries and therefore people have been shifted to other different occupation than farming. The ratio of cultivators in 1971 was more than 75 percent that comes near to 11 percent and number of other workers increased by 74 between the forty years. Special economic activities for Engineerings and related Industries are at Kalwara, Bhambhoriya, Bagru Khurd and Jhai villages. Sitapura has become under for special economic zone. According to Master Development Plan 2025, Bagru, Watika, Shivdasapura & Chandlai are the growth centers that will be connected to NH 8 and NH 12. The socio-economic characteristics of the study area, population growth, Industrialization, nearness to walled city and development to road network have caused the general changes of land use and occupational structure.

KEYWORDS: *land use, occupational structure, SEZ, population growth*

INTRODUCTION

Land is valuable natural resources for human being especially for agricultural countries like India. Land use is the surface utilization of all the developed and vacant land on a specific point at given time and space (Jalal 1970). Advancement of science and technology introduced a new breed of urban culture which is more service oriented. This modifies the occupational structure considerably (Giri 1976). The change in occupational structure of people is a major index for the measurement of the economic development. Today occupational structure is attributed to most of urban

population growth and change in agricultural land or labour.

OBJECTIVE

The present study aim to analysis the trends of population growth and land use change over the forty years and its effects on changing characteristics of working population in Sanganer Tehsil of Jaipur Tehsil.

THE STUDY AREA

Sanganer tehsil is one of the tehsil of Jaipur district consisting of 147 villages and three growth centre's .it is attached with Jaipur city with geographical coordinates in north and in east. It is located between 26° 49' to 26° 51' N latitude and 75° 46' to 75° 51' E longitudes. The climate of the area is hot and semiarid with extremes of temperature between 15° to 45 °c having average rainfall around 650 mm. It is estimated that 25% population of Sanganer is directly or indirectly dependent on Sanganer print industries for their livelihood. The total area of Sanganer is about 635.5 sq. km. out of which 129 sq km² comprise urban area the rest 622 sq km² is rural area. Sanganer is a central hub for industrial practices of block printing over 300 years to the region of Maharaja Sawai Jai Singh. Most of the industries of Sanganer are situated in the urban areas. This tehsil having population 9,69,696 is one of the most prosperous amongst thirteen tehsils of Jaipur district. It is estimated that 25% population of Sanganer is directly or indirectly dependent on sanganeri print industries for their livelihood. There are at present huge cluster of block and screen printing units in Sanganer. Presently the river saraswati has dried up completely and waste water of the city flows through it.

MAP OF STUDY AREA

METHODOLOGY

An attempt is made to examine the changes that have occurred in population, land use and occupational characteristics during the 40 years (1971-2011). For the present study data of six major categories of land uses and occupational structure have been analyzed. The data for the present study is obtained mainly from secondary sources i.e. district census handbooks and district gazetteers. Statistical tools like percentage, average, charts and tables used in the study.

GROWTH OF POPULATION

The intensive use of land depends upon the population concentration, Industrial location, communication and transportation. Table 1 gives the population of Sanganer tehsil and its changing trend at each census year from 1971 to 2011. The population has gradually increased from 1971 to 2011. During these years the population has increased by 22 percent. It is clear that population is growing at a rapid rate during the decades 1981-1991 and 2001-2011 but there is great growth of population in 2001 that was 178.42 percent over decadal growth.

TABLE 1: GROWTH OF POPULATION AND DENSITY OF SANGANER TEHSIL

	Population			Population Density	
	Rural	Urban	Total	Decade Growth in %	Density (sq.km.)
1971	87592	11617	99209	-	156
1981	121842	21941	143783	44.92	226
1991	153893	51972	205865	43.17	297
2001	131301	441870	573171	178.42	625
2011	174892	704803	969695	69.15	1455

Source: Various Census Handbook 1971-2011

According to 2011 census the population of Sanganer tehsil was 9.69 lakh spread over its area of 665 sq. km. giving the overall density of 1455 persons per sq. km. The density of population during four decades has increased by 1299 persons per sq.km. (Table 1 and graph 2). As per census 2011 the major villages of tehsil Watika had density of 485 persons/ per sq. km. Muhana had 530 persons, Dahmi Kalan had 650 persons and Jaisinghpura had 800 persons per sq. km. Shriram ki Nangal is only village that had 2532 persons per sq. km.

FIGURE 1: SANGANER TEHSIL - POPULATION GROWTH FROM 1971-2011

Source: Computed by the Researcher

The high density is mainly observed in the parts of the tehsil where the industrial development, improvement in transportation network, urbanization, availability of dyers and SEZ projects. Mohamed Ait Belaid (2003) concluded that the effects of urbanization are main factor for changing the land use pattern of rural and urban areas. Jaitpura, Bagru, Hirawala, Chhitroli and Sitapura have maximum number of industrial units and IT parks. The Sanganer International Airport has important attraction of national and international industrial projects.

FIGURE 2: POPULATION DENSITY OF SANGANER TEHSIL

Source: Computed by the Researcher

The maximum urbanization is observed in the areas where the road network is more developed such as Watika, Sitapura, Kalwar, Muhana, Dahmi Kalan and Bagru. As result of it, urbanization in Sanganer tehsil has increased from almost 12 percent to almost 82 percent during four decades which has been increased due to rural population migration for employment, education and better standard of life.

LAND USE PATTERN

Land use is the function of four variables- land, water, air and man. Land constitutes to its body, water through its veins life blood; air gives it oxygen and man acts as the dynamic actor to reflect its types, pattern and distribution (singh R.P., 1992). The land use of the study area is discussed in six categories viz: (1) Forest (2) Land put to non agricultural uses (3) Barran and uncultivable land (4) Fallow Land (5) Net Sown area and (6) Cultivable waste land. The table 2 – shows the trend of these land use changes in the study area.

FOREST

Forest is not only an essential for the maintenance of the ecological equilibrium but also their role is important for primary employers. Sanganer tehsil had only 0.78 percent area under the forest in the first decade (1971-1981) that marginally decreased by 0.58 percent during after decades.

TABLE 2: SANGANER TEHSIL- LAND USE PATTERN (1971-2011)

Sr.No.	Land Use Categories	Land Use Pattern of 1971(%)	Land Use Pattern of 2011(%)
1	Forest	0.78	0.61
2	Net sown Area	63.52	40.46
3	Culturable Waste	16.66	5.7
4	Barran & Non cultivable land	11	4.62
5	Cultivable Land	5.81	9.19
6	Non agricultural uses	2.23	39.42
	Total	100	100

Source: District census Handbook 1971-2011

LAND PUT TO NON AGRICULTURAL USES

This category includes the land occupies by the buildings, roads, railways, factories, villages, towns, water bodies and playground etc. It occupied 2.04 of the total area of the tehsil in 1970-71 which greatly increased to 35.78 percent after these decades. It started rising and reached to second largest land use category. In the next three decades

(1980-81 to 2010-11) area under this category has continuously increased by 1.19 percent per year. It is due to rising population the development of roads network and increased the area of built up.

FIGURE 4: (A) LAND USE PATTERN OF SANGANER TEHSIL 1971

(B) LAND USE PATTERN OF SANGANER TEHSIL 2011

Source: Computed by the Researcher

BARRAN AND NON CULTIVABLE LAND

Barran and non cultivable land includes outcrops of hills and mountains. This land is associated with poor soil, heavy rainfall and intense erosion (vaidhya, 1997). Out of the total geographical area, the study area had 5.81 percent under this category in 1971 which increased up to 7019 percent in 2011. During these four decades it had rapidly increased 1.38 percent. In Sitapura, Bagru and Watika used such type of land for warehouses or storage to get the assurance of fixed incomes hence such type of land is used for fundamental structure day by day.

FALLOW OR CULTIVABLE LAND

This type of land has decreased by 5.58 percent to 16.66 percent during 1971 to 2011 (table 2 and fig.4). It was decreased by rapid rate with 11.08 percent in the study area due to lack of irrigation sources and availability of saline contents in water bodies, SEZ, IT parks and Industries. This tehsil has been irrigating their fields from a feeder of the Dravyavati river containing toxic discharge from the Sanganeri print and Dye industries that located nearby.

NET SOWN AREA

Area under category decreased by 63.52 percent and 40.45 respectively in the four decades (1971 to 2011). The maximum area affected by salinity is found in Sanganer after Dudu and Phulera tehsils. The total area is 2667.50 hac. affected by this hydro drastic challenge (S.C. Kalwar).

CULTIVABLE WASTE LAND

The stream (Dravyavati) was traditional source of irrigation for the region but these decades; old unauthorized Industrial and domestic set up have polluted the water. There is no alternative source of irrigation for the farmers.

OCCUPATIONAL STRUCTURE

The relationship between the agricultural transformation in the study area and the resultant economic development is viewed in this study. The study of occupational structure is an essential to observe the economic development of the area. A significant consequential relationship between the establishment of textiles Industries and the Employment trend is analyzed here.

An industrial with an occupation belongs to the active groups of population. Following Colin Clark (1972), it is customary to classify it into three groups. These are, the primary sector (including agriculture, forestry, hunting and fishing), Secondary (mining, quarrying, manufacturing and production), and Tertiary activities (commerce, transportation, communication and services of all types).

TABLE 3: OCCUPATIONAL STRUCTURE OF SANGANER TEHSIL

CATEGORY	YEARS				
	1971	1981	1991	2001	2011
Cultivators	75.77	60.52	50.53	22.3	11.43
Agr.labourer	8.61	5.2	8.16	3.9	1.81
House hold	6.75	5.57	3.14	5.1	3.81
Others	8.85	28.68	38.15	68.7	82.93
Total	100	100	100	100	100

Source: District census handbook 1971-2011

PRIMARY GROUP OF WORKERS

In 1971 the maximum number of people came under this category that has 84.38% out of total workers. In this group agricultural laborers and cultivators included which were continuously decreased by 18.65 percent in 1981. In the next three decades this ratio rapidly decreased with the rate of 58.69 percent, 26.2 percent and 13.24 percent in 1991, 2001 and 2011. Primary workers transformed their work and involved in secondary and tertiary activities. Due to poor quality of ground water and adverse effects on irrigation, salinity hazard is alarming in the study area (Metha et.al 2014). There are many organic and inorganic pollutants, heavy metals pesticides and fluoride in groundwater.

FIGURE 5: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF OCCUPATIONAL STRUCTURE OF SANGANER TEHSIL

Source: computed by the researcher

SECONDARY GROUP OF WORKERS

In this category the number of worker were less than 10 percent from the year 1971 till 2011 and the number of the workers decreased by 2.43 percent to 1.29 no percent in the 1981-19991 and 2001-2011. But there is noticeable that the workers increased in these activities in 1991-2001.

TERTIARY GROUP OF WORKERS

The number of these type of workers are symbol of development and rapid industrialization. These workers rapidly increased in four decades by 4.08 percent. Due to lack of irrigation facilities farmers and agricultural laborers accepted printing and dying work for their livelihood. At present 315 printing units area settled in this tehsil. These textiles industries discharged pollutants from dying and printing that have caused serious pollution problems of water bodies and land in Sanganer.

CONCLUSIONS

It is concluded that the growth of population and urbanization is continuously and steadily increasing in the study are. The population increased by 9.77 times during 1971-2011. The average annual population growth from 1971 to 2011 was about 21.05 %. The density of population increased from 156 persons to 1455 persons per sq.km. To reduce the high pressure of population growth on net sown area and textiles industries, the reliable irrigation facilities are required for the development of vegetable market in the study are.

Sanganer is the administrative headquarter that has all the urban facilities which attracts surrounding rural people to this urban area due to Sitapura SEZ, Bagru industrial area and printing units are the main attraction for rural people showing an interest for abandoned the primary activities and migrant from their rural area. Thus it has been observed that the spatial and the temporal land use changes are due to the growth of population and resultant industrialization.

Population and industrialization growth bring the change in land use particularly in net sown area, fallow land and forest area. It is observed that the overall decrease in net sown area is 23.06 % and it is mostly in the urbanized and industrialized are particularly such as Sitapura, Bagru, jaitpura, chhitroli and the surrounding village. The decrease in net sown are is mostly because of urban population pressure and industrialization. There is a slight and continuous increase in the area under non agricultural during these four decades. The area under the forest is not increased as to be the expected. For maintaining the environmental balance in the area under forest should be increased. It is observed that farmers near the urban area utilize their land for construction purposes because they want to earn stable income, that is not constant in monsoon based gamble farming and cultivable waste land is used for the ware houses in the village. Therefore the cultivators have joined to another economic activity due to land is acquired for income to small scale industries and favorable hydro conditions. It is observed that the number of cultivators and agricultural laborers' has rapidly decreased during four decades by 64.34 and 6.81 percent respectively. Another household industrial worker suffers through ups and downs but from the last decade (2001-2011) their participation in the total number of workers have decreased due to textile industries going at room in their local bodies. On the basis because of their viewed for Dravyavati river is cleared. It is observed that the farmers of the area are pressurized for irrigating their crops from that polluted and harmful not mineralized and toxic colored water. A drastic fall in ground water table was observed by farmers. The other irrigation sources have submerged in that area due to decreasing level of ground water table. Soil fertility is decreasing due to consumption of chemical and ails by the textiles industries.

On the basis of field survey it was found that the only 3 percent farmers are full time cultivates while other (98.78) percent are involved or joined to other economic activities due to more paying. It was observed that more than 75 percent farmers have small land holding size that they used for seasonal fruits/vegetables cropping pattern.

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